

UNIQUENESS OF MODERN RUSSIAN WOMEN'S PROSE

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Abstract: This article explores the peculiarities and unique features of modern women's prose, revealing its originality in the context of modern literary culture. The author analyses trends, stylistic features, themes and methods of artistic representation inherent in women writers, and also discusses the influence of socio-cultural and gender factors on the formation of women's literary identity.

Keywords: modern women's prose, literary culture, trends, stylistic features, themes, methods of depiction, gender factors, literary identity.

Russian women's prose as a mass phenomenon appeared in the late 80s - early 90s of the XX century. At that time, various collective collections of women's prose were published. Women writers actively declare the need to acquire a female voice in the literary scene, trying to prove that women writers write no worse, and even better, than male colleagues.

Numerous female names have entered modern Russian literature: S.Vasilenko, L.Petrushevskaya, T. Tolstaya, L.Ulitskaya, M.Paley, V.Narbikova and others. Among them, it is necessary to single out L.Petrushevskaya.

Lyudmila Stefanovna Petrushevskaya is a playwright and novelist. The story "Such a Girl" was sent to the editorial office of the New World in 1968, but the editor A.T. Tvardovsky refused to print it.

Since the early 70s, Petrushevskaya has been acting as a playwright. At the turn of the 80s and 90s, Petrushevskaya turned mainly to prose. The first stories appeared on the pages of the magazine "Aurora" in 1972. From the late 80s to the end of the century, Petrushevskaya published a number of collections of short stories and novellas. The novel "Time is Night" was awarded the Booker Prize for 1992. Petrushevskaya occupies a very important place in Russian prose, and is considered the ancestor of modern women's prose. Her works have been translated into many languages of the world. Today, Petrushevskaya is one of the most researched writers not only in Russia, but also abroad.

It is worth noting that Petrushevskaya's work causes acute controversy among readers and critics as soon as her first work was published. On the one hand, there are critics who see in Petrushevskaya's prose emptiness, indifference, rudeness, lack of spiritual strength and artistic taste. On the other hand, many critics consider the writer to be a true master of realism, an honest witness to public life. It is impossible not to pay attention to the words of the

critic G.V.Viren, who in his critical article "Such Love" writes that "She (Petrushevskaya) sympathizes with them (women), experiences their dramas, lives their lives. Without Petrushevskaya's work, our literature would not be complete" [Viren 1989: 203]. It emphasizes the quintessence of Petrushevskaya's work — female characters, and gives the writer a proper assessment.

Of course, from the first stories Petrushevskaya's themes have been unchanged: illness, death, suffering and loneliness of women attract special attention of the writer, women's issues are always at the center of Petrushevskaya's narrative.

In our opinion, one of the most characteristic features of women's prose of the 80s and 90s is the overcoming of the traditional male/female dichotomy. According to literary critic T.A.Meleshko, masculine and feminine in modern women's prose enter into more complex relationships, form new models of interaction between the sexes. Meleshko believes that the elimination of femininity is characteristic of L.'s artistic manner. Petrushevskaya: a woman finds herself in a tragic situation of forced masculinization, which leads to the death of both the masculine and the feminine [Meleshko 2001].

The images of the female destroyer in Petrushevskaya's stories and novels are very revealing: modern Medea (the story "Medea"), the Soviet lady with a dog (the story "The Lady with Dogs"), the tyrant mother Terrible (the story "Little Terrible"), the namesake of Anna Akhmatova (the story "Time is Night"), testifying to the irreversible the process of masculinization of a woman who is dying and bringing death. And therefore, despite the fact that Petrushevskaya's heroine is outwardly presented as a battered creature crippled by everyday life, she does not appear small, downtrodden and humiliated at all. As T.Kasatkina noted, a woman is a whole world, to which a man treats as a part of the whole. In comparison with a woman, a man in Petrushevskaya's works appears as an imperfect being and a "fat child" who understands nothing and is irresponsible [Kasatkina 1996].

Here is a typical example of the disappearance of both the feminine and the masculine in the story "Little Terrible": a man does not have the masculine qualities of a traditional hero at all, but appears weak, stupid. And the heroine is Formidable — strong, determined, single-handedly controls everyone and everything, does not let anyone live. Femininity has finally died in the heroine, there is no maternal love (she drove two sons out of the family) and affection for her husband (she often scolds him).

It is noteworthy that at least a man is present in this story, in many other works of Petrushevskaya the family exists in the form of a purely "female", there are only female members: grandmother, mother, daughter (the story "Time is Night", the story "Zina's Choice", the story "The Jewess Verochka"). In her work, Petrushevskaya unfolds before readers the realities of the life of a Soviet woman — being a participant and victim of the myth of pseudo-feminism, she has to bear a double burden — social and domestic. The man either goes to another woman, or is not known at all. The heroines clearly see the impasse of a woman as a housewife and at the same time a breadwinner. This is the main factor in the "disappearance" of women and femininity in Petrushevskaya's work. However, despite the sensational exposure and ruthless cruelty, Petrushevskaya does not offer any recipes for life change. The impact of her works has been compared to shock therapy. In 1991, in a Harvard lecture "The Language of the Crowd and the Language of Literature," Petrushevskaya spoke about the need for the terrible in art. In her opinion, this is a rehearsal for death, plunging the reader into catharsis, after which there is a rebirth to life [Cit. by: Meleshko 2001]. Obviously, this is the pathos of the annihilation strategy of overcoming the traditional male/female opposition in Petrushevskaya's work..

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